

Using Hydrogen Recombination Masers to Study Disk and Wind Kinematics in MWC 349A

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Abstract

The kinematics of circumstellar disks and disk winds are poorly understood due to the difficulty of producing well resolved observational data. The bright hydrogen recombination-line maser emission originating from the circumstellar disk of MWC 349A offers a unique opportunity to study the disk at milli-arcsecond precision. Using high angular resolution observations of the maser emission from MWC 349A carried out by the SMA, we were able to produce and analyze rotation curves for the H26 α , H30 α , and H31 α transitions. We found that maser features originating from the disk follow Keplerian motion. Furthermore, the H31 α masers in the disk appear to form in a narrow annulus at a fixed radius from the star, consistent with previous studies of the H30 α and H26 α masers. Based on analysis of the rotation curves for the three maser transitions, there appears to be an inverse relationship between the frequency of the maser emission and the radial extent to which the corresponding maser emission spans. This implies that maser transitions for lower quantum numbers occur in the inner and denser regions of the disk than the higher quantum transitions. Using the scaling relationship between quantum number and radius of emission for each maser transition, we derived the density distribution throughout the disk, which follows the relation $n_e \sim R^{-4.9 \pm 0.6}$. Finally, we found that a stellar mass of $M = 10 \pm 3 M_\odot$ was most consistent with the kinematics of the maser features originating from the Keplerian disk.

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Chapter 1

Introduction and Background

1.1 Maser Emission

An astrophysical maser (Microwave Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation) is a source of stimulated emission typically in the millimeter and centimeter wavelengths. Spectral emission occurs when an atom or molecule undergoes a transition from a higher to a lower energy level, emitting radiation in spectral lines. The frequency, ν , of this radiation is determined by the amount of change in energy:

$$\nu = \frac{\Delta E}{h} \tag{1.1}$$

where ΔE is the energy difference between the upper and lower levels, and h is Planck's constant. In order to produce a maser, however, a population inversion is required (Gray, 2012). Under conditions of thermodynamic equilibrium, population levels follow the Boltzmann distribution, producing

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thermal emission with excitation temperatures equal to the kinetic temperature of the gas. For such cases, the ratio of the number of electrons in two given states is:

$$\frac{N_2}{N_1} = \frac{g_2}{g_1} \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{kT}\right) \quad (1.2)$$

where g_1 and g_2 are the degeneracies of the energy levels ($g_n = 2n^2$ in the case of hydrogen), k is the Boltzmann constant, and T is the kinetic temperature of the gas (Elitzur, 1992). In some circumstances, however, if the system departs from thermodynamic equilibrium, a population inversion can occur. A population inversion is the state in which the number of electrons in highly excited energy states exceeds that of electrons under thermodynamic equilibrium (Elitzur, 1982).

A population inversion occurs when an energy level is over populated as a result of exchanges with other energy levels. This population exchange can be described by loss rates and pump rates. The pump process is a transition from a lower to higher energy level caused by external radiation or collisions, allowing the higher energy level to become more populated. For the population inversion to occur, the pump rate of the upper state must be larger than that of the lower state. Masers are formed in inverted populations since they provide an amplifying medium where stimulated emissions exceed absorption (Elitzur, 1992).

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There are two types of masers – saturated and unsaturated. For unsaturated masers, the intensity of the maser is weak enough that when particles are emitted from the system by loss events, the population difference is able to return to its original value before another radiative interaction takes place. In other words, the population inversion will not be exhausted by the maser emission. Consequently, the population difference is determined by the pump scheme rather than the intensity of the maser. As a result, unsaturated masers can vary substantially over time due to fluctuations in pump rates (Elitzur, 1982, 1992).

In contrast, for saturated masers, interactions between photons and molecules occur so quickly that other processes cannot take place to replenish the population inversion. Molecules pumped into the system are soon excited and emitted, producing a high maser intensity. This high rate of emission affects the size of the population inversion and, eventually, results in weakened maser emission (Elitzur, 1982, 1992).

Few molecules have been observed producing maser emission. These molecules include OH, H₂O, SiO, methanol (CH₃OH), and ammonia (NH₃). Strong maser emission has also been observed in HII regions where bright, young stars ionize their surrounding gas (Elitzur, 1992). Further information specific to hydrogen masers is discussed by Strel'nitski, Ponomarev and Smith (1996) and Strel'nitski, Smith and Ponomarev (1996).

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Maser emission has been observed in various astrophysical environments, including comets, planetary and stellar atmospheres, molecular clouds, and circumstellar disks around hot stars. In the case of hot stars, radiation from the star can excite molecules in a circumstellar disk, producing masers. The spectral lines from these masers encode information about the disk from which they originate, describing the disk kinematics (including rotational velocities) via Doppler shifts. Because maser emission is inherently bright and compact, it provides an ideal opportunity for long baseline interferometry, which offers precise spatial resolution of the maser features (Gray, 2012).

Understanding the kinematics of circumstellar disks can shed light on the formation and evolution of massive protostars. Circumstellar disks have a significant role in the evolution of protostars, allowing the protostar to grow in mass via accretion of matter from the disk. In order for this process of accretion to continue, the disk must lose angular momenta of infalling matter through outflow caused by winds. However, the kinematics of disks and the origins of these winds is poorly understood. There is little observational evidence that outflows carry angular momentum. This is because spectral line emission from jets and outflows is often broad, causing the detection of rotation signals across the jet axis to be difficult (Chen et al., 2016).

1.2 MWC 349A

MWC 349A is a hot, massive Herbig B[e] star with a circumstellar disk of gas that is ionized by the stellar radiation, producing saturated, strong hydrogen recombination-line masers in the millimeter and infrared wavelengths. These masers occur in the α transitions ranging from $n = 7$ in $H7\alpha$ to $n = 39$ in $H39\alpha$ (Martin-Pintado et al., 1989; Streltinski, Ponomarev and Smith, 1996; Thum et al., 1992, 1994, 1995). The transitions for $n > 39$, however, produce thermal recombination lines (Zhang et al., 2017). MWC 349A is not the only source that exhibits recombination-line masers, however; other objects such as η Carinae, Cepheus A HW2, and MonR2 have been observed emitting radio recombination-line masers (Cox et al., 1995; Jiménez-Serra et al., 2011, 2013).

MWC 349A is a binary star located at a distance of 1.2 kpc (Cohen et al., 1985) and is estimated to have a mass as large as $\sim 30 M_{\odot}$ (Ponomarev et al., 1994; Thum et al., 1992). MWC 349A is believed to be a young star, though recent observations suggest that it may be a massive evolved LBV star (Gvaramadze and Menten, 2012). The bright maser emission originating from its circumstellar disk offers a unique opportunity to study the kinematics of the disk and wind (Martín-Pintado et al., 2011). Due to the small spatial scale of the maser features, long baseline interferometry is required in order to observe this object with sufficient angular resolution (Gray, 2012).

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Several observations of MWC 349A have been made using the Submillimeter Array (SMA) at a high angular resolution and high signal-to-noise, allowing the positions of maser features to be measured with a precision of 2 milli-arcseconds (mas) (e.g. Weintroub et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2017).

The first high resolution observation of the maser emission from MWC 349A was in 1992 by the Owens Valley Radio Observatory (OVRO) interferometer at 232 GHz. Measurements of the relative positions the strongest H30 α maser emission indicate that the masers originate from an edge-on circumstellar disk (Planesas et al., 1992). The presence of this disk was confirmed by a previous IR observation, which exhibited extinction excess that could be caused by a dusty disk (Cohen et al., 1985). Furthermore, Planesas et al. (1992) noticed that the emission was concentrated towards the east and west of the star, producing a double-peaked spectrum as shown in Figure 1.1. This double peaked profile is explained by Ponomarev et al. (1994) to be the result of amplification from a narrow annulus within the disk. An edge-on Keplerian disk generally produces a triplet spectral shape due to the significant amount of masing material at the center of the disk as shown in Figure 1.2 in the lightly-shaded boxes. However, if the emission originates from a narrow enough ring within the disk, the central component will be much weaker, creating a double-peaked spectrum. The narrow maser rings are speculated to be the result of high electron densities in the inner regions of the disk, which create an optically thick environment where the medium

Figure 1.1: The double-peaked spectrum observed by Planesas et al. (1992) for the indicated baselines. This image was reproduced from Planesas et al. (1992).

Figure 1.2: For an observer viewing an edge-on Keplerian disk, the longest amplification paths are shown by the lightly shaded boxes. For a narrow enough ring of amplification, however, the central component becomes very weak compared to the side components, creating a double-peaked spectrum (Ponomarev et al., 1994). This image was reproduced from Ponomarev et al. (1994).

is more thermalized. This environment restricts the population inversion that allows the masers to form from higher quantum transitions (Ponomarev et al., 1994).

More recent observations of the H30 α and H26 α maser emission from MWC 349A have confirmed the theory proposed by Ponomarev et al. (1994) that the masers originate from narrow rings in the disk. Observations of the H30 α maser at 230 GHz using the Submillimeter Array (SMA) and the IRAM Plateau de Bure interferometer have shown that the emission occurs in discrete locations about the star (Weintroub et al., 2008; Martín-Pintado et al., 2011). Further observations by Zhang et al. (2017) at 353 GHz of the H26 α line revealed that the H26 α masers came from locations within the H30 α masers, closer to the center of the disk. Rotation curves of the maser emission, shown in Figure 1.3, demonstrate that the H26 α masers with velocities between -10 to 30 km s⁻¹ were distributed linearly and more steeply compared to the distribution of the H30 α masers. This implies that the H26 α masers originate from a denser, inner part of the disk, moving at higher orbital velocities than the H30 α masers. An illustration of the locations of the two masers is shown in Figure 1.4 (Zhang et al., 2017).

The linear shape of the rotation curve for the maser emission with LSR velocities (V_{LSR}) between -10 and 30 km s⁻¹ is consistent with Keplerian rotation. To explain this linear structure in the rotation curve, imagine a

Figure 1.3: A comparison of the rotation curves for H26 α and H30 α . It is evident that the H30 α emission extends further away from the star than the H26 α emission. This indicates that the H30 α masers originate from locations farther out in the disk while the H26 α masers come from an inner ring within the disk, consistent with theoretical models (Strel'nitski, Smith and Ponomarev, 1996; Zhang et al., 2017). Image reproduced from Zhang et al. (2017).

Figure 1.4: An illustration of the locations of the H26 α and H30 α masers on the disk. The H26 α masers are located on the inner ring while the H30 α masers originate from the outer ring. For a distant observer, the tangential component of the maser emission will follow a linear structure (Zhang et al., 2017). Image reproduced from Zhang et al. (2017).

distant observer viewing the disk edge-on. The line-of-sight velocity, V_{LSR} , is given by,

$$V_{\text{los}} = V_{\text{orbit}} \sin \phi \quad (1.3)$$

where V_{orbit} is the orbital velocity of the masers and ϕ is the angular offset of the maser from the position of the star. For Keplerian motion, this can also be expressed as,

$$V_{\text{los}} = l \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R^3}} \quad (1.4)$$

where $l = R \sin \phi$ is the projected distance, G is the gravitational constant, M is the enclosed mass, and R is the radius of the masing ring. Equation 1.4 clearly demonstrates the linear relation between the line-of-sight velocity and the projected distance. Masers with $V_{\text{LSR}} > 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ or $< -20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, however, no longer follow this linear disk-like structure and are caused by wind (Zhang et al., 2017).

The rotation, as well as approximations for the mass loss in the disk, indicate significant angular momenta in the wind (Báez-Rubio et al., 2014). This provides evidence that the disk wind is responsible for the loss of angular momenta in the disk, allowing the process of accretion of matter to continue in the star. However, the SMA observations used in this analysis had poor phase stability and required self-calibration of the data. This meant that a precise kinematic model of the system could not be determined (Zhang et al., 2017).

Follow-up SMA observations of the H26 α and H31 α maser lines were carried out in dual receiver mode with higher sensitivity than previous observations (Zhang et al., 2017). The goal of this project is to access a new hydrogen-recombination maser line at high resolution, namely the H31 α transition maser, in order to better define the model presented by Zhang et al. (2017) of the maser emission within the circumstellar disk. Furthermore, we hoped to improve the accuracy of the data and analysis of the H26 α transitions conducted by Zhang et al. (2017) in order to register the spatial distributions on scales smaller than 0.1 mas and to more completely describe the disk and wind kinematics in the MWC 349A system. However, due to the poor signal-to-noise in the bandpass calibrator data, the H26 α transition data were not usable, and we were unable to address the second goal.

Chapter 2

Methods/Theory

2.1 Interferometry

The angular resolution of a diffraction-limited telescope is inversely related to the diameter of the telescope and is given by:

$$\theta = 1.22 \frac{\lambda}{D} \quad (2.1)$$

where λ is the wavelength of observation and D is the diameter of the telescope. The largest radio telescopes that have been created thus far have diameters on the order of $D \approx 100$ m. One of the largest radio telescopes, the Arecibo Observatory, has a diameter of 305 m and produces an angular resolution of almost 0.6 arcminutes at a wavelength of 5 cm¹. This approximate upper-limit on angular resolution significantly limits our ability to observe

¹<http://websites.suagm.edu/ao/?q=the-305m-telescope>

objects with small spatial scales. Interferometry, however, has introduced a way in which we can achieve sub-arcsecond resolution².

2.1.1 Young's Double-Slit Experiment

Basic interferometry is based on Young's double slit experiment. The antennas can be thought of as the slits in Young's experiment, and incident light from a point source is observed as a fringe pattern due to the difference in distance that light has to travel to reach each antenna. The separation of the fringes is given by the wavelength of the light divided by the distance between the slits (or antennas in this case). An extended source can be considered as a sequence of point sources where the observed fringe pattern is simply the sum of the fringe patterns from each point source. For a point source offset from the center (i.e. the pointing of the antennas), the fringe pattern is simply phase-shifted by a distance proportional to the angular offset of the point source. Figure 2.1 depicts the effect of an extended source on the fringe pattern. A source with angular size greater than λ/b (where b is the separation of the antennas) cannot be resolved. The fringe visibility, v , is defined as:

$$v = \frac{I_{max} - I_{min}}{I_{max} + I_{min}} \quad (2.2)$$

²Jim Condon, <https://science.nrao.edu/opportunities/courses>

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Figure 2.1: The Young double slit experiment with fringe patterns for various extended point source distributions. Panel (a) shows the simple double slit fringe pattern from a single point source where the maxima are separated by a distance of λ/b . Panel (b) shows the effect of increasing the angular size of the source by adding additional point sources. A source with an angular offset of θ shifts the fringe pattern, or introduces a phase, of θ in the opposite direction. In panel (c), the angular size of the extended source has exceeded λ/b , so the visibility is zero and no features can be distinguished from the source. However, if the same extended source were observed by antennas with smaller separation, the source would no longer wash out the fringes (Jackson, 2008). Image adapted from Jackson (2008).

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where I_{max} is the maximum intensity and I_{min} is the minimum intensity. The expression for the intensity, I , in the fringe pattern is given by:

$$I = I_0 \cos^2 \left(\frac{\phi}{2} \right) \quad (2.3)$$

where I_0 is the central peak intensity, and ϕ is the phase of the fringe pattern. The visibility for a source larger than λ/b is zero since the fringe pattern is constant. However, if the antennas are placed further apart, then λ/b becomes smaller and the source can be resolved. Alternatively, if the source has an angular size much smaller than λ/b , then the visibility is 1. This means that the source is smaller than the angular resolution of the interferometer, so it will only be seen as a point source with no significant features. Figure 2.2 shows how the visibility changes with antenna separation for spatially extended sources compared to spatially compact sources. For spatially compact sources, the visibility remains high for large antenna separations, while for spatially extended sources, the visibility drops quickly (Jackson, 2008). Thus for sources with small spatial scales (such as maser emission from a circumstellar disk), a more extended antenna array (maintaining visibility) is preferable to be able to detect small features, while for extended sources, a tighter antenna array is required. Note that an interferometer consisting of N antennas can simply be considered as $N(N - 1)/2$ independent baseline pairs (Jackson, 2008).

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Figure 2.2: The relation between visibility and antenna separation for large, extended sources compared to small sources (Jackson, 2008). Image taken from Jackson (2008).

2.1.2 Basic Two-Element Interferometer

Thus far, I have illustrated the basic concept behind interferometry. However, the way in which the signal received by the antennas is processed and interpreted involves more complex mathematics. Consider the diagram shown in Figure 2.3. For two antennas separated by a baseline vector \vec{b} , plane waves from a source in the direction \hat{s} will have to travel an additional distance of $\vec{b} \cdot \hat{s} = b \cos \theta$ before they reach antenna 1. Thus, antenna 1 and antenna 2 will receive the same signal, but with a geometric time delay of $\tau_g = \vec{b} \cdot \hat{s} / c$ where c is the speed of light. This can also be considered as a phase delay of $\phi = k \vec{b} \cdot \hat{s}$, where $k = 2\pi / \lambda$ and λ is the wavelength of the observation. For a quasi-monochromatic interferometer (one that observes on a very narrow band centered at $\nu = \omega / (2\pi)$), the output voltages for each antenna are given

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Figure 2.3: A diagram of a two-element interferometer. The output voltages, V_1 and V_2 , are equal, but are offset by a geometric time delay, τ_g . The correlator multiplies and averages the output voltages from the two antennas. This output response from the correlator has an amplitude, R , as shown in the diagram. The broad Gaussian envelope of the response is due to primary-beam attenuation³.

Image from <http://www.cv.nrao.edu/course/astr534/Interferometers1.html>

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by:

$$V_1 = V \cos[\omega(t - \tau_g)], \quad V_2 = V \cos(\omega t) \quad (2.4)$$

where V is the voltage amplitude and t is time. The correlator combines these voltages by taking their product and then averaging over time to find the response, R , of the interferometer:

$$V_1 V_2 = \left(\frac{V^2}{2}\right) [\cos(2\omega t - \omega\tau_g) + \cos(\omega\tau_g)] \quad (2.5)$$

$$R = \langle V_1 V_2 \rangle = \left(\frac{V^2}{2}\right) \cos(\omega\tau_g) \quad (2.6)$$

The response, R , is equivalent to the fringe pattern from the double-slit experiment discussed in Section 2.1.1, and the phase of the fringe pattern as a function of the change of source direction is given by:

$$\phi = \omega\tau_g = \frac{\omega}{c} b \cos \theta \quad (2.7)$$

where θ is the angular direction of the source. The fringe phase provides an accurate measure of the position of the source with respect to the pointing of the antennas. For an extended source, the response will be the sum of point-source fringe patterns coming from each point on the source, as shown in Figure 2.1. Thus, by using Fourier transforms, each of the sinusoidal components of the response can be extracted to determine the signal from each part of the source. By introducing more baselines (i.e. antennas), and thereby

more Fourier components, the point-source response of the interferometer and the point spread function (PSF) approach a Gaussian with an angular resolution of approximately λ/b , where b is the longest projected baseline in the array of antennas (Jackson, 2008).

2.1.3 Extended Sources and the uv -Plane

For a source coming from the angular direction $\hat{\sigma}$ with respect to the antenna pointing, \hat{s} , the response of a two-element interferometer is given by:

$$R = \int I(\sigma) e^{ikb \cdot \hat{\sigma}} d\hat{\sigma} \quad (2.8)$$

where $I(\sigma)$ is the intensity of the source at the location $\hat{\sigma}$, and $k = 2\pi/\lambda$. This expression for R is simply the Fourier transform of the source intensity distribution. It can be re-written as a two dimensional Fourier transform: \hat{b} becomes $u\mathbf{i} + v\mathbf{j}$, where u is the east-west component of the baseline, and v is the north-south component of the baseline; and $\hat{\sigma}$ becomes $\sigma_x\mathbf{i} + \sigma_y\mathbf{j}$. Note that u and v are defined in units of wavelength, allowing λ to be removed from the expression. Thus, Equation 2.8 can now be written as (Jackson, 2008):

$$R(u, v) = \iint I(x, y) e^{2\pi i(ux+vy)} dx dy \quad (2.9)$$

At this point, retrieving the image of the source should be a simple inverse Fourier transform of $R(u, v)$ to find $I(x, y)$. However, this is not the case;

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remember that interferometer observations are not continuous, but rather readings are sampled at different parts of the u, v plane specified by the sampling function, $S(u, v)$, which is equal to 1 in parts of the u, v plane that are sampled, and 0 otherwise. Thus, after taking an inverse Fourier transform, what we have is called the dirty map:

$$I_D(x, y) = \iint R(u, v) S(u, v) e^{2\pi i(ux+vy)} du dv \quad (2.10)$$

Using the convolution theorem, which states that the Fourier transform of a product is the convolution of their separate Fourier transforms, we can rewrite Equation 2.10 as:

$$I_D(x, y) = I(x, y) * B(x, y) \quad (2.11)$$

where $I(x, y)$ is the image and $B(x, y)$ is the Fourier transform of the sampling function, called the dirty beam. From here, you can solve for the image using a deconvolution. To do this, there is an algorithm called CLEAN which performs a brute force deconvolution (Jackson, 2008). For more details on the CLEAN algorithm, see Chapter 2 of *Principles of Interferometry* by N. Jackson.

Figure 2.4: An illustration of the propagation of the antennas during Earth's rotation and the projected baselines⁴.

2.1.4 Earth-Rotation Synthesis

Astronomical objects can often be complex on small spatial scales. This requires that the interferometer have a high-quality PSF so that side lobes in the final image (resulting from imperfections in the deconvolution due to the discreteness of the samples) are not confused for elements of the image. Arrays with a limited number of antennas and limited antenna separation often have insufficient uv coverage and, therefore, a noisy instantaneous PSF (Haykin and Liu, 2009).

In order to cover more of the uv -plane, Ryle et al. (1950) determined a technique called Earth-rotation aperture synthesis, which utilizes the Earth's

⁴Image taken from <http://www.cv.nrao.edu/course/>

rotation as a method for varying the projected baseline coverage of an interferometer. Figure 2.4 shows an illustration of the baselines resulting from this technique (Ryle et al., 1950).

2.2 Calibration

Before the interferometer data can be analyzed, calibration must be performed in order to remove any variability with time caused by changes in Earth's atmosphere and the instrument. There are three main categories of data calibration (Taylor et al., 1999):

1. *Direct calibrations* – Feedback circuitry and close monitoring of the components within and around the array system can be used to correct for variations in gain caused by the receiver system (Taylor et al., 1999).
2. *Calibrator sources in the sky* – In order to determine the antenna phase offsets accurately, a sky calibrator is necessary as a reference source. Furthermore, periodic observations of calibrators can be used to track phase and gain stability. Also, the atmosphere can cause variability in phase over time, which can be monitored by frequent observations of a calibrator source. Note that observations of calibrator sources occur separately from the observations of the actual source, and are often located at different positions in the sky (Taylor et al., 1999).

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3. *Self-calibration* – In some instances, if the science object being observed is a bright point source with known structure, the source itself can be used to calibrate the data (Taylor et al., 1999).

Many aspects of the calibration and corrections occur on-line and during the observations (Taylor et al., 1999). We will focus on the methods of calibration that utilize calibrator sources in the sky and are applied after the observations have been made.

Atmospheric opacity affects the visibility amplitude of the observation by decreasing the strength of the source signal and by introducing noise from the atmospheric emission. The extent of these effects can be measured by observing calibrators with known flux density at various elevations (Taylor et al., 1999). By tracking the system temperature at different elevations, the contributions of atmospheric attenuation (highest at low elevations and lowest at zenith) can be accounted for by multiplying the system temperature with the visibility amplitude and weighting the data accordingly. This correction improves the signal-to-noise ratio of long observations and can also remove effects from weather changes (Qi, 2015).

Beyond the system temperature correction, there are three main calibrations, namely the bandpass calibration, gain calibration, and flux calibration. The bandpass calibration accounts for changes in gain with frequency across the bandwidth of observation. It requires the observation of a strong source

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(often quasars are used for this) for its high signal-to-noise ratio. Furthermore, the calibrator source must have a flat spectrum across the frequency band of observation. Thus, fluctuations in the gain of the calibrator spectra can be measured and used to normalize the data. After successful calibration, the phase and amplitude in the calibrator spectra should be flat (Taylor et al., 1999).

The gain calibration accounts for time-dependent gain variations that are caused by atmospheric and weather changes over larger timescales (greater than five minutes). This calibration requires periodic observations of a non-variable point source with known flux density and position in the sky. Ideally, this source should be close enough to the science target so that it is within the angular scale of irregularities from the atmosphere (Thompson et al., 2017). Optimally, in some cases, if the observing target is a strong enough point source and has a known structure, it can be used for self-calibration. Because the calibrator source should be non-variable, one can assume that variations in the gain with time are due to external factors, and necessary adjustments can be made (Taylor et al., 1999).

Finally, the flux calibration uses an object of known flux (often planets are used for this) in order to convert from visibility amplitude to flux. In cases where the flux of the science target is known, the conversion can be made without the use of a separate calibrator (Qi, 2015).

2.3 Extracting Position Information

Once the calibrations have been performed such that the amplitude and phase for the gain calibrators are flat, the visibility data of the science target can be used to produce images. In some cases, if the science target has a small enough angular size compared to the angular resolution, λ/b , and a high enough signal-to-noise ratio in the data, more precise position information can be extracted on the target source.

As depicted in Figure 2.1, an extended source can be considered as many point sources, each of which contributes another phase-shifted sinusoidal wave to the observed signal (Jackson, 2008). Using Fourier transforms, one can extract each individual sine wave corresponding to a different spatial part of the extended emission. The phase corresponding to each sine wave encodes information on the location of the emission with reference to the central point of observation. The technique of centroid fitting to visibility data makes use of the phase information to determine the position (Zhang et al., 2017).

If the visibility phases are well determined throughout the spectral features, this allows for astrometry with better precision than the spatial resolu-

2.3. EXTRACTING POSITION INFORMATION

tion. Consequently, the precision is dictated by the phase noise and, thereby, the signal-to-noise ratio of the data by the relation:

$$\Delta\theta_{\text{fit}} = \frac{\theta_{\text{beam}}}{2 \text{ SNR}} \quad (2.12)$$

where $\Delta\theta_{\text{fit}}$ is the position error (i.e. precision), θ_{beam} is the size of the synthesized beam, and SNR is the signal-to-noise ratio in the data (Zhang et al., 2017).

Note, however, that additional error is added to the position values due to errors in the bandpass solution. This error can be improved by averaging over channels to increase the signal-to-noise during the bandpass calibration. In doing so, the position error becomes:

$$\Delta\theta_{\text{BP}} = \theta_{\text{beam}} \frac{\Delta\phi}{360^\circ} \quad (2.13)$$

where $\Delta\theta_{\text{BP}}$ is the error in position due to the bandpass calibration and $\Delta\phi$ is the reduced phase error after averaging. Thus, given the position errors due to centroid fitting and bandpass calibration, the total error on position can be written as (Zhang et al., 2017):

$$\Delta\theta = \sqrt{\Delta\theta_{\text{fit}}^2 + \Delta\theta_{\text{BP}}^2} \quad (2.14)$$

Chapter 3

Observations

3.1 The Submillimeter Array

The Submillimeter Array (SMA) is a radio interferometer consisting of eight 6-meter diameter telescopes. It is located on the top of Mauna Kea in Hawaii. Figure 3.1 is an image of the SMA atop the summit. The interferometer operates at frequencies ranging from 180 to 418 GHz and can be placed into four different configurations, allowing for baselines as large as 509 meters. Each antenna is equipped with receivers in four different frequency bands and has the capability of dual frequency operation. Recently, the digital correlator backend has been extended with the SWARM correlator (SMA Wideband Astronomical ROACH2 Machine), which allows for a wider bandwidth of 8 GHz per sideband per receiver¹.

¹SMA Observer Center, <http://sma1.sma.hawaii.edu/status.html#arrayconf>

Figure 3.1: The Submillimeter Array on Mauna Kea in Hawaii².

3.2 Data Acquisition and Calibration

3.2.1 Observations

Four attempts at the observations of MWC 349A were made by the SMA on July 11, and August 3, 2016 in the Very Extended configuration, and on October 14, and October 22, 2016, in the Extended configuration. For the first two observations in July and August, all eight antennas were in operation, covering baseline lengths from 68 to 509 m. The source was observed in dual frequency mode with the 230 GHz and 400 GHz receivers, corresponding to the H31 α and H26 α masers with rest frequencies of 210.50178 GHz and 353.6228 GHz respectively. The spectral resolution of the observations

²Image from <http://sma1.sma.hawaii.edu/smaoc.html>

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

produced by SWARM is 140 kHz per channel, which corresponds to a 0.2 km/s resolution at the H31 α maser line frequency. The zenith opacity at 225 GHz, measured by the CSO τ -meter, was approximately 0.07 on July 11, and 0.1 on August 3. For the July 11 observation, the atmospheric phases were generally stable throughout the observation. The system temperatures varied between around 90 and 150 K for the 230 GHz receivers and 230 and 600 K for the 400 GHz receivers. For the August 3 observation, the atmospheric phases stabilized after 3 hours into the observation. The instability for the first three hours was due to poor weather conditions early in the observation, during which the opacity was above 0.3. The system temperatures varied between 80 to 170 K for the 230 GHz receivers and between 230 to over 600 K for the 400 GHz receivers.

For the last two observations on October 14 and 22, seven of the eight antennas were in operation, covering baseline lengths from 44 to 226 m. The source was only observed with the 400 GHz receivers in an attempt to improve the data for the H26 α masers. The zenith opacity at 225 GHz was approximately 0.04 on October 14, and 0.08 on October 22. In both observations, the atmospheric phases were stable. For the October 14 observation, the system temperatures varied between around 190 and 400 K for the 230 GHz receivers and 200 and 420 K for the 400 GHz receivers. For the October 22 observation, the system temperatures varied between 150 to 600 K for the 230 GHz receivers and between 200 to over 600 K for the 400 GHz receivers.

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

The phase center for the observations of MWC 349A was at $\alpha_{J2000} = 20^{\text{h}}32^{\text{m}}45.528^{\text{s}}$, $\delta_{J2000} = +40^{\circ}39'36.623''$. For all four observations, in order to monitor the time-dependent gain variation, periodic observations of 2015+371 were made. Note that due to the fact that MWC 349A is a bright point source, self-calibration can be used for the gain calibration. Additionally, 3C454.3 was observed for the bandpass calibration, and Titan, Neptune, and Uranus for the flux calibration. Table 3.1 contains more detailed information on the observation of MWC 349A and the calibrator sources.

Table 3.1: SMA Observations

UT Date	Exposure Time	Number Antennas	Baseline Range (m)	τ (225 GHz)	Calibrators		
					Flux*	Bandpass	Gain
2016 Jul 11	14h 56m	8	68–490	0.07	Titan & Neptune	3C454.3 & 3C279	2015+371
2016 Aug 03	12h 17m	8	68–490	0.1	Titan & Neptune	3C454.3 & 3C279	2015+371
2016 Oct 14	13h 19m	7	44–226	0.05	Uranus	3C454.3 & 3C84	2015+371
2016 Oct 22	9h 39m	7	44–226	0.07	Uranus	3C454.3 & 3C84	2015+371

* Note: the continuum flux of MWC 349A is known to be relatively stable over time. The SMA sometimes uses it as a flux calibrator.

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

Due to the better phase stability and weather conditions on July 11, the first observation was used for the H31 α maser data. Unfortunately, the bandpass calibrator observations for the 400 GHz receivers were insufficient to produce accurate data for the H26 α maser.

3.2.2 Calibration

The calibrations were performed using the MIR software package, written in IDL (Qi, 2015). First, system temperature corrections were applied to remove variations in atmospheric absorption at different elevations of observation. Figure 3.2 shows a plot of the system temperature for the 230 GHz observation as a function of elevation. Each of the sources observed is colored differently in the plot. These system temperature values were then used to remove system temperature contributions from the atmosphere.

The flux calibrations using Neptune and Titan were unnecessary since the flux of the continuum emission of MWC 349A was already determined in previous observations. Zhang et al. (2017) found that the continuum flux densities for MWC349A are 1.7 Jy at 230 GHz and 2.4 Jy at 345 GHz. To account for the time-dependent gain variation, we were able to implement self-calibration, using the continuum emission of MWC 349A itself.

The bandpass calibration was performed using observations of 3C454.3.

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

Figure 3.2: The system temperature at 230 GHz is plotted as a function of elevation of observation. The plot is colored differently for each object observed. As expected, the system temperature is significantly larger at lower elevations due to the larger airmass closer to the horizon.

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

Figure 3.3: The raw spectra of 3C454.3 at 230 GHz, including both amplitude (upper plots) and phase (lower plots), are plotted as a function of channel for both ASIC and SWARM. Because this source is a bright, non-variable quasar, the amplitude and phase of the observation should be constant. Thus, fluctuations in phase and amplitude are due to electronic effects as well as atmospheric variations. After calibration, these fluctuations should be removed.

Due to poor quality of the 400 GHz data, it had to be calibrated separately from the 230 GHz data. For the 230 GHz data, the raw spectra of 3C454.3 are plotted in terms of channels, and are shown in Figure 3.3. At this point, the phase and amplitude vary across the channels and in frequency. The phase and amplitude of the 3C454.3 spectra are then fitted in MIR as shown in Figure 3.4. Note that the ASIC and SWARM channels were fit separately in order to avoid inaccurate calibration due to the inherent differences of the

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

Figure 3.4: The bandpass solution for the 3C454.3 observation at 230 GHz is shown by the red curve fitting the phase and amplitude. This fit is used to normalize the amplitude and phase in order to remove any gain fluctuations with frequency.

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

Figure 3.5: The spectra of 3C454.3 at 230 GHz after the bandpass calibration has been applied. Notice that both the amplitude and phase have become flat, as desired, and the spectra from ASIC and SWARM are aligned well.

correlators. The resulting bandpass solution is then used to normalize the phase and amplitude in order to remove gain fluctuations with frequency. After the bandpass solution is applied, the spectrum should be flat. Figure 3.5 shows the bandpass-calibrated spectrum of 3C454.3. It can be seen that both the phase and amplitude are flat, and, moreover, that the ASIC and SWARM spectra are mostly consistent with the phases lining up together.

The same bandpass solution was applied to the MWC 349A spectrum, and the result is shown in Figure 3.6. The spectrum in Figure 3.6 demonstrates that the calibration was successful since the baseline amplitude is

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

Figure 3.6: The spectra of the H31 α masers from MWC 349A are plotted in terms of frequency instead of channels. Having been calibrated, the baseline for the amplitude is consistently flat and peaks at the spectral feature due to the maser emission. Note that at the location where the amplitude peaks, there is greater signal-to-noise, allowing the phase to be better constrained. The phase fluctuation corresponding to the location of the amplitude peaks can be used to determine the positions of the maser spots.

3.2. DATA ACQUISITION AND CALIBRATION

consistently flat. Furthermore, there is a clear double-peaked feature from the H31 α maser emission, which has a shape consistent with previous observations (similar to that of Figure 1.1 in Planesas et al. (1992)). Note that at the location where the amplitude peaks, there is greater signal-to-noise, allowing the phase to be better constrained. The phase variations across the maser spectrum can be used to determine the positions of the maser emission. The calibrated visibility data of H31 α emission were then exported to the MIRIAD format for further data analysis.

A similar procedure was followed for the bandpass calibration of the 400 GHz data, corresponding to the H26 α maser observation. However, due to the poorer quality of the upper sideband data (USB), the fit was performed only on the lower sideband (LSB) data of 3C454.3 and was applied to both the USB and LSB data. Unfortunately, despite several attempts at observations, the signal-to-noise ratios in the bandpass data were insufficient to accurately constrain the positions of the H26 α data. Thus, we opted to use the previously acquired observations of H26 α made in 2012 and analyzed by Zhang et al. (2017). Note that all further discussion of the H26 α data refers to the data collected by Zhang et al. (2017).

Chapter 4

Results and Analysis

4.1 *Uvfit* Results

The fully calibrated data of the H31 α maser emission from MWC 349A, having been saved in MIRIAD format, were then applied to the *Uvfit* script assuming a point source distribution. *Uvfit* determines the flux and position of the emission for each spectral channel (Zhao, 2012). The script also provides errors on the reported values based on the signal-to-noise of the emission. Section 2.3 explains the basic theory behind the determination of the position offsets. Further documentation on the script is provided by Zhao (2012) in the MIRIAD user guide. Note that the *Uvfit* data for the H26 α and H30 α data had already been generated by Zhang et al. (2017). We used these data to produce the following figures and calculations.

4.1. UVFIT RESULTS

The spectra of the H26 α , H30 α and H31 α maser lines are shown in Figure 4.1 and are colored by the velocity of the channel. The two emission peaks occur around -16 km s^{-1} and 31 km s^{-1} for all three maser transitions. The peak on the redshifted side is approximately twice the value of the blue-shifted side in all three spectra. The flat part of the spectrum between the two peaks has a flux larger than 5 Jy and as large as 8.5 Jy for the H26 α transition.

The positions determined by *Uvfit* are reported as offsets in arcseconds from the center in both right ascension and declination, where the center is the pointing of the antennas (at phase zero). Figure 4.2 shows the plotted position offsets for the H26 α , H30 α and H31 α maser spots. The plots are colored by the Doppler-shifted velocities of the maser emission as it rotates about the star. The H26 α and H30 α maser positions are plotted for velocities between -28 km s^{-1} and 48 km s^{-1} in order to avoid data points with low signal-to-noise. The H31 α maser positions are plotted for velocities between -27 km s^{-1} and 47 km s^{-1} . In all three plots, there is a clear flat, horizontal structure, tracing the circumstellar disk around MWC 349A. The velocity gradient extends from the southeast on the redshifted side of the disk, to the northwest, on the blue-shifted side of the disk (Zhang et al., 2017). At the ends of these features, particularly on the redshifted side of the disk extending beyond 20 km s^{-1} , there are strong maser features departing from the disk. These divergent features behave differently in all three maser transi-

4.1. UVFIT RESULTS

Figure 4.1: Spectra of the H31 α , H30 α and H26 α maser transitions. The color bar on the left side of the panel denotes the LSR velocity of the maser feature.

4.1. UVFIT RESULTS

Figure 4.2: Spatial distribution of maser emission in $H31\alpha$, $H30\alpha$ and $H26\alpha$ transitions. The offset positions in RA and DEC are measured with respect to the phase center. The color bar on the left side of the panel denotes the LSR velocity of the maser features. For $H26\alpha$, the phase center was shifted to the maser feature around 31 km s^{-1} due to self calibration.

tions. It is believed that they are produced by ionized winds of gas that are lifted off the plane of the disk (Martín-Pintado et al., 2011).

4.2 Rotation Curves

In order to better understand the kinematics of the disk traced by the maser emission, we produced rotation curves. Rotation curves demonstrate the relation between the LSR velocity, V_{LSR} , of maser components in the disk and the wind as a function of the projected distance. The projected distance, l is the distance from the center of the disk as it is projected in the sky and is determined by the expression:

$$l = \text{sign}(\Delta\alpha)\sqrt{\Delta\alpha^2 + \Delta\delta^2} \quad (4.1)$$

where $\Delta\alpha$ is the position offset in RA and $\Delta\delta$ is the position offset in DEC (Zhang et al., 2017). Figure 4.3 shows the plots for the preliminary rotation curves of the three maser transitions. The rotation curves follow a linear structure in the maser emission extending from approximately -10 km s^{-1} to 25 km s^{-1} in all three transitions. As described in Section 1.2, this linear shape is consistent with Keplerian rotation, following the relation in Equation 1.4. The maser emission at velocities less than -10 km s^{-1} and greater than 25 km s^{-1} depart from the linear shape and are likely due to the wind

4.2. ROTATION CURVES

Figure 4.3: Preliminary rotation curves for the H31 α , H30 α and H26 α transitions using the data presented in Figure 4.2. The color bar on the left side of the panel denotes the LSR velocity of the maser features.

4.2. ROTATION CURVES

in the disk. Interestingly, the shapes of the wind features are different in each of the three transitions.

However, from these plots in Figure 4.3, it is clear that the position offsets are not centered correctly, namely because the zero position on the projected distance axis is not centered with respect to the linear portion of the curve. This is particularly evident in the H26 α transition rotation curve, where the phase center was shifted to the maser feature around 31 km s⁻¹ km/s due to self calibration. In order to address this issue, we had to determine a corrected center position in the disk. We did so by fitting a linear regression to the position offset plots, weighting the fit by the error bars. Again, the fit was limited to the maser emission originating from the disk and not the winds, thus a velocity interval was set between approximately -10 km s⁻¹ to 25 km s⁻¹. The center of the linear fit would then be used as the new center for the disk. Figure 4.4 shows the plotted position offsets with the linear fits for the three maser transitions. The red stars mark the determined position of the disk center. For the linear fits to be consistent, the slopes of the fits for all three transitions should be similar since they trace the inclination of the disk. We found that all three slopes were similar, with values consistent within error bars (the slope values are shown within Figure 4.4); furthermore, the slopes implied disk inclinations of approximately 8°, consistent with previous calculations (Martin-Pintado et al., 1993; Tafuya et al., 2004). The fit for the H26 α maser transition yielded a center offset of $(\Delta\alpha, \Delta\delta) =$

4.2. ROTATION CURVES

Figure 4.4: The center of the disk was determined by fitting an error-weighted linear regression to the spatial distributions of the H31 α , H30 α and H26 α transitions. The midpoints of the fits for each maser transition were denoted as the center positions and are marked by a red star. The color bar on the left side of the panel denotes the LSR velocity of the maser features.

4.2. ROTATION CURVES

$(-0.0195 \pm 0.0004, 0.0013 \pm 0.0004)$ arcseconds; the fit for the H30 α transition yielded a center offset of $(\Delta\alpha, \Delta\delta) = (-0.0016 \pm 0.0003, 0.0010 \pm 0.0003)$ arcseconds; and the fit for the H31 α transition yielded a center offset of $(\Delta\alpha, \Delta\delta) = (-0.0027 \pm 0.0002, 0.0028 \pm 0.0002)$ arcseconds.

Applying the new centers to the rotation curves, the plots were better centered around zero in projected distance, l , and the rotation curves appear more continuous and well-behaved. A weighted linear regression was then applied to the linear portion of the rotation curves between -10 km s^{-1} and 25 km s^{-1} in order to determine the slopes of the Keplerian motion. These slopes are equivalent to the coefficient in the Keplerian motion equation:

$$\frac{dV_{los}}{dl} = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R^3}} \quad (4.2)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, M is the enclosed mass, which is approximately equal to the mass of the star, and R is the radius at which the maser emission occurs.

The fitted rotation curves for the three maser transitions are shown in Figure 4.5, along with the slopes of the fits. The rotation curve for the H26 α maser transition only extends out to 0.022 arcseconds from the center on either side, while the rotation curves for H30 α and H31 α extend out to approximately 0.025 and 0.026 arcseconds from the center, respectively. The

4.2. ROTATION CURVES

Figure 4.5: Fitted rotation curves after re-centering for the H31 α , H30 α and H26 α transitions. The color bar on the left side of the panel denotes the LSR velocity of the maser features.

4.2. ROTATION CURVES

slope for the H26 α transition is $871.0 \pm 9.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$; the slope for the H30 α transition is $689.5 \pm 4.2 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$; and the slope for the H31 α transition is $675.8 \pm 4.8 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Radial Extents of the Maser Transitions

The rotation curves for the H26 α (green), H30 α (blue), and H31 α (red) maser transitions are plotted together in Figure 5.1 for ease of comparison. The data are offset so that the LSR velocity is zero at the zero position. The intercepts of the linear fits for each maser transition were subtracted from the data. These velocity offsets correspond to the systemic velocity of the star MWC 349A. The systemic velocity derived from the H26 α transition fit is $6.98 \pm 0.15 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; similarly, we found a systemic velocity of $6.91 \pm 0.09 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from the H30 α fit. These values are consistent with the systemic velocities derived by Zhang et al. (2017) and Thum et al. (1994). However, the fit for the H31 α transition determined a systemic velocity of $9.34 \pm 0.10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, which is inconsistent with the values for the other two

Figure 5.1: The three rotation curves for the H26 α (green), H30 α (blue), and H31 α (red) maser transitions are plotted together for comparison. The linear fits for each respective curve are plotted over the data in the corresponding color, demonstrating the inverse relationship with the slope of the fit and the quantum transition number. The black curves represent the radial extents of Keplerian motion for a given stellar mass. The dashed line traces the radial extent for a star of mass $M = 10 M_{\odot}$, the dashed-dotted line traces the radial extent for a star of mass $M = 15 M_{\odot}$, and the dotted line traces the radial extent for a star of mass $M = 30 M_{\odot}$. It appears that a mass of $M = 10 M_{\odot}$ is most consistent with our data.

5.1. RADIAL EXTENTS OF THE MASER TRANSITIONS

transitions. This is likely due to the fact that the flat portion of the flux between -15 and 20 km s^{-1} , which largely corresponds to the Keplerian portion of the disk, is smallest for the $\text{H}31\alpha$ transition. This lower signal-to-noise could contribute to the difference in values for systemic velocity.

The data in Figure 5.1 clearly demonstrate that the slopes are directly related to the maser transition frequency (or inversely related to the quantum transition number). Furthermore, there is an apparent direct relationship between the quantum transition number and the radial extent of the Keplerian portion of the curve between -10 km s^{-1} and 25 km s^{-1} . Using the expression for Keplerian motion (introduced in Equation 1.4), we can produce Keplerian rotation curves for a given stellar mass. By equating projected distance with radial extent, we have the expression for a Keplerian motion curve:

$$V_{los} = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R}} \quad (5.1)$$

where G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the star, and R is the projected distance in the rotation curve. In order to use Equation 5.1, we must convert from angular size to distance. Given that the distance of MWC 349A is 1.2 kpc , we calculated the conversion between arcseconds and meters to be $1.80 \times 10^{14} \text{ arcsec m}^{-1}$. In Figure 5.1, Keplerian motion curves are plotted for masses of $M = 10 M_{\odot}$, $M = 15 M_{\odot}$ and $M = 30 M_{\odot}$. The Keplerian curve for the mass $M = 10 M_{\odot}$ appears to be most consistent

5.1. RADIAL EXTENTS OF THE MASER TRANSITIONS

with the data; thus we assume a stellar mass of $M = 10 \pm 3 M_{\odot}$. The error on this value was determined using Equation 4.2 to propagate the errors on the projected distances at the ends of the disk and on the fitted slopes for each maser transition. Using 0.0018 arcseconds as the error on the projected distances, the slopes produced mass errors of $2.8 M_{\odot}$, $2.9 M_{\odot}$, and $3.1 M_{\odot}$ for H31 α , H30 α , and H26 α respectively.

This new mass estimate is significantly smaller than the previous predictions of $M = 30 M_{\odot}$. This is due to the fact that previous mass estimates used the velocity at the peak of the maser spectrum, which corresponds to features in the wind (Ponomarev et al., 1994). The spectral peak also corresponds to a larger radius from the center of the disk. Consequently, since both the velocity and the radius were overestimated, this lead to a large mass estimate.

To find the radial extents for each maser transition, we used the equation for coefficient of Keplerian motion, solving for R :

$$R = \left(\frac{GM}{\left(\frac{dV_{los}}{dt}\right)^2} \right)^{1/3} \quad (5.2)$$

Then using slopes of the rotation curves for the three masers and adopting $M = 10 \pm 3 M_{\odot}$ for the mass of MWC 349A, we determined the radial distances of emission for each maser transition. The resulting values are re-

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Table 5.1: Radial Extents for the H26 α , H30 α , and H31 α Maser Transitions.

Maser Transition	Disk Radius (arcsecs)	Disk Radius* (AU)
H26 α	0.022	25.63 ± 2.57
H30 α	0.025	29.95 ± 2.10
H31 α	0.026	30.36 ± 3.04

* Assuming a source distance of 1.2 kpc.

ported in Table 5.1.

5.2 Density Profiles

Having determined the radial extents for each of the maser transitions, we can now derive a relationship between the electron density and the radial extent in order to better understand the distribution of matter throughout the disk. First we must determine the relationship between the frequency of the maser emission and its corresponding radius of extent. To do this, we fit an error-weighted power-law to the radial extent as a function of emission frequency. The resulting fit is shown in Figure 5.2, plotted in a log-log scale. The radius was found to follow a power-law relation with an exponent of -0.338 , as shown in Equation 5.3:

$$R \sim \nu^{-0.338 \pm 0.024} \tag{5.3}$$

5.2. DENSITY PROFILES

Figure 5.2: The radial extents as a function of the frequency of observation are plotted in the red points on a log-log scale. The three points were fitted with a power-law relation, shown by the black curve, that was weighted by the errors in radius. The exponent in the power-law relation is found to be -0.338.

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where R is the radial extent of the maser emission, and ν is the frequency of maser emission. This relationship is consistent with the previous results from Zhang et al. (2017) within error. Furthermore, this relation suggests that the density within the disk decreases with radius, which follows predictions of models for non-LTE maser emission.

In creating maser models specific to hydrogen recombination, Strel'nitski, Ponomarev and Smith (1996) determined a relationship between the upper quantum number of the maser transition and the electron density in the disk region using population departure coefficients derived by Storey and Hummer (1995). The relation is shown in Equation 5.4:

$$n_{max} \sim n_e^{-0.18} \quad (5.4)$$

where n_{max} is the upper quantum number and n_e is the electron density. Using a different method of derivation, Thum et al. (1994) determined the relationship between upper quantum number and electron density to follow the expression:

$$n_{max} \sim n_e^{-0.22} \quad (5.5)$$

We reconcile the exponents in Equations 5.4 and 5.5 to estimate the relation between upper quantum number and electron density to be:

$$n_{max} \sim n_e^{-0.20 \pm 0.02} \quad (5.6)$$

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Furthermore, we know that for ionized hydrogen, the upper quantum number scales with frequency by the following expression (Gordon and Sorochenko, 2009):

$$n_{max} \sim \nu^{-1/3} \quad (5.7)$$

Given the scaling relationships between upper quantum number and electron density, and between quantum number and frequency, we can determine an expression for the scaling between frequency and quantum number:

$$\nu \sim n_e^{0.6 \pm 0.06} \quad (5.8)$$

This, in turn, can be used to derive a relationship between the disk radius and the electron density:

$$R \sim n_e^{-0.203 \pm 0.025} \quad (5.9)$$

Or equivalently:

$$n_e \sim R^{-4.9 \pm 0.6} \quad (5.10)$$

These results for the density distribution are consistent with the exponent values determined by Zhang et al. (2017) within error, though our exponent of -4.9 ± 0.6 is much larger than the radial density profile of r^{-2} for classical accretion disks (Keto and Zhang, 2010; Pringle, 1981). However, the derivation for our density profile shown in Equation 5.10 depends on the models that determine the scaling relationship in Equation 5.6. We speculate that these models incorrectly describe the relation between upper quantum num-

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ber and electron density.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

Using high angular observations of hydrogen recombination-line masers from MWC 349A carried out by the SMA, we were able to produce and analyze rotation curves for the H26 α , H30 α , and H31 α transitions. Our main findings are:

1. Maser features originating from the disk follow Keplerian motion. This occurs around the V_{LSR} interval from -10 km s^{-1} to 25 km s^{-1} for the three maser transitions.
2. H31 α masers in the disk form in a narrow annulus at a fixed radius from the star, in a similar manner as the H30 α and H26 α masers.
3. Based on analysis of the H26 α , H30 α , and H31 α maser transition rotation curves, there appears to be an inverse relationship between the upper quantum number of the maser transition and the disk radius

to which the corresponding maser emission spans. This implies that maser transitions for lower quantum numbers occur in denser regions of the disk than the higher quantum transitions.

4. The density throughout the disk follows the relation $n_e \sim R^{-4.9 \pm 0.6}$. This relation is significantly steeper than the density profile for a classical accretion disk.
5. In comparing the Keplerian motion curves to the rotation curves for the three maser transitions, we found that a stellar mass of $M = 10 \pm 3 M_\odot$ was most consistent with the maser features originating from the disk.

Bibliography

- Báez-Rubio, A., Martín-Pintado, J., Thum, C., Planesas, P. and Torres-Redondo, J. (2014), ‘Origin of the ionized wind in MWC 349A’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **571**, L4.
- Chen, X., Arce, H. G., Zhang, Q., Launhardt, R. and Henning, T. (2016), ‘Rotating Bullets from A Variable Protostar’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **824**, 72.
- Cohen, M., Bieging, J. H., Dreher, J. W. and Welch, W. J. (1985), ‘The binary system MWC 349’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **292**, 249–256.
- Cox, P., Martín-Pintado, J., Bachiller, R., Bronfman, L., Cernicharo, J., Nyman, L.-A. and Roelfsema, P. R. (1995), ‘Millimeter recombination lines towards Eta Carinae’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **295**, L39–L42.
- Elitzur, M. (1982), ‘Physical characteristics of astronomical masers’, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **54**, 1225–1260.
- Elitzur, M., ed. (1992), *Astronomical masers*, Vol. 170 of *Astrophysics and Space Science Library*.
- Gordon, M. A. and Sorochenko, R. L. (2009), *Radio Recombination Lines: Their Physics and Astronomical Applications*, Vol. 282 of *Astrophysics and Space Science Library*.
- Gray, M. (2012), *Maser Sources in Astrophysics*.
- Gvaramadze, V. V. and Menten, K. M. (2012), ‘Discovery of a parsec-scale bipolar nebula around MWC 349A’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **541**, A7.
- Haykin, S. and Liu, K. J. R. (2009), *Handbook on Array Processing and Sensor Networks*.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Jackson, N. (2008), Principles of Interferometry, *in* F. Bacciotti, L. Testi and E. Whelan, eds, ‘Jets from Young Stars II’, Vol. 742 of *Lecture Notes in Physics*, Berlin Springer Verlag, p. 193.
- Jiménez-Serra, I., Báez-Rubio, A., Rivilla, V. M., Martín-Pintado, J., Zhang, Q., Dierickx, M. and Patel, N. (2013), ‘A New Radio Recombination Line Maser Object toward the MonR2 H II Region’, *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters* **764**, L4.
- Jiménez-Serra, I., Martín-Pintado, J., Báez-Rubio, A., Patel, N. and Thum, C. (2011), ‘Extremely Broad Radio Recombination Maser Lines Toward the High-velocity Ionized Jet in Cepheus A HW2’, *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters* **732**, L27.
- Keto, E. and Zhang, Q. (2010), ‘The standard model of star formation applied to massive stars: accretion discs and envelopes in molecular lines’, *Monthly Notices of the RAS* **406**, 102–111.
- Martin-Pintado, J., Bachiller, R., Thum, C. and Walmsley, M. (1989), ‘A radio recombination line maser in MWC349’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **215**, L13–L16.
- Martin-Pintado, J., Gaume, R., Bachiller, R., Johnston, K. and Planesas, P. (1993), ‘Simulated Ratio Recombination Line Emission at 1.3 Centimeters toward MWC 349’, *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters* **418**, L79.
- Martín-Pintado, J., Thum, C., Planesas, P. and Báez-Rubio, A. (2011), ‘Disk and wind kinematics in MWC 349 A’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **530**, L15.
- Planesas, P., Martin-Pintado, J. and Serabyn, E. (1992), ‘Positions of the radio recombination line masers in MWC 349’, *The Astrophysical Journal, Letters* **386**, L23–L26.
- Ponomarev, V. O., Smith, H. A. and Strel'nitski, V. S. (1994), ‘Modeling of the hydrogen maser disk in MWC 349’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **424**, 976–982.
- Pringle, J. E. (1981), ‘Accretion discs in astrophysics’, *Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics* **19**, 137–162.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Qi, C. (2015), *The MIR Cookbook*.
- Ryle, M., Smith, F. G. and Elsmore, B. (1950), ‘A preliminary survey of the radio stars in the Northern Hemisphere’, *Monthly Notices of the RAS* **110**, 508.
- Storey, P. J. and Hummer, D. G. (1995), ‘Recombination line intensities for hydrogenic ions-IV. Total recombination coefficients and machine-readable tables for $Z=1$ to 8’, *Monthly Notices of the RAS* **272**, 41–48.
- Strelitski, V. S., Ponomarev, V. O. and Smith, H. A. (1996), ‘Hydrogen Masers. I. Theory and Prospects’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **470**, 1118.
- Strelitski, V. S., Smith, H. A. and Ponomarev, V. O. (1996), ‘Hydrogen Masers. II. MWC 349A’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **470**, 1134.
- Tafoya, D., Gómez, Y. and Rodríguez, L. F. (2004), ‘Imaging MWC 349 from 7 Millimeters to 90 Centimeters’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **610**, 827–834.
- Taylor, G. B., Carilli, C. L. and Perley, R. A., eds (1999), *Synthesis Imaging in Radio Astronomy II*, Vol. 180 of *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*.
- Thompson, A. R., Moran, J. M. and Swenson, Jr., G. W. (2017), *Interferometry and Synthesis in Radio Astronomy, 3rd Edition*.
- Thum, C., Martin-Pintado, J. and Bachiller, R. (1992), ‘Monitoring of the recombination line maser in MWC349’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **256**, 507–518.
- Thum, C., Matthews, H. E., Harris, A. I., Tacconi, L. J., Schuster, K. F. and Martin-Pintado, J. (1994), ‘Detection of $H21\alpha$ maser emission at 662 GHz in MWC 349’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **288**.
- Thum, C., Strelitski, V. S., Martin-Pintado, J., Matthews, H. E. and Smith, H. A. (1995), ‘Hydrogen recombination β -lines in MWC 349.’, *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **300**, 843.
- Weintraub, J., Moran, J. M., Wilner, D. J., Young, K., Rao, R. and Shin-naga, H. (2008), ‘Submillimeter Array Imaging of the Maser Emission from the $H30\alpha$ Radio Recombination Line in MWC 349A’, *The Astrophysical Journal* **677**, 1140–1150.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Zhang, Q., Claus, B., Watson, L. and Moran, J. (2017), ‘Angular Momentum in Disk Wind Revealed in the Young Star MWC349A’, *ArXiv e-prints* .

Zhao, J. (2012), *Basic Information on uvfit*.